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Preservice Bilingual Teacher Training in the Multicultural Conditions of Tatarstan

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Abstract

The relevance of this article is explained by the fact that the globalization processes taking place in the system of world education determine the tendency to create a multilingual educational environment, which contributes to the formation of a multilingual personality who knows and respects not only own native language and national culture, but also speaks other languages well and is well orientated in the traditions of other nations.

The purpose of the article is to consider the creation and justification of the theoretical foundations of a multilingual educational environment at the higher education level as a condition for the professional training of future bilingual teachers who are able to teach their subject in two languages. The leading approach to the study of the problem of forming a multilingual educational environment for the professional training of a future bilingual teacher is based on the identification and systematic analysis of its specific features.

The article discusses the theoretical aspects of creating a multilingual educational environment in the Republic of Tatarstan. Based on the analysis of the literature and our own experience of scientifically practical activity, author's definitions of the concepts "multilingual educational environment" and "bilingual teacher" are proposed. The article substantiates that a multilingual educational environment, acting as one of the requirements for modern education, needs a specific approach and the definition of effective forms of work with students. The article may be of interest to specialists involved in the study of issues in the field of multilingual education.

Keywords: multilingual educational environment, polilingualism, multilingualism, bilingual teacher.

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Introduction

A competent combination of traditions of national and world culture is one of the priority tasks for the development of the regions of the Russian Federation in the context of globalization. Within the educational sphere of domestic regions, one of the urgent is problem of preservation of national identity, which involves the training and education of the younger generation in a spirit of respect for national culture. In the Republic of Tatarstan (RT), not only cultural policy, but also educational policy is aimed at preserving national-cultural identity. To support the national and cultural interests of residents of the Republic of Tatarstan, given the general trends of world development, it becomes possible based on the principle of multilingualism.

Polylinguality is quite a widespread phenomenon and is integral to the development of various spheres of human activity, it is a rather complex and multifaceted phenomenon that requires detailed study and a concretization in relation of we are interested field of education.

Currently, Tatarstan is becoming increasingly relevant in the implementation and realization of polylingual education aimed at the formation of the polylingual personality of a future teacher-bilingual. The urgency is due to the fact that the principles of polylingual educational environment reflected in the content of the State program of the Republic of Tatarstan ‘Preservation, studying and development of state languages and other languages in the Republic of Tatarstan for 2014-2020’ (Resolution Of The Cabinet Of Ministries Of The Republic Of Tatarstan, 2013), where the Central position is the creation of a unified educational environment and development of the polylingual personality. In addition, under the Federal national project «Education» provides for the implementation of innovative programs for high schools, which will be directed on formation at future teachers of polylingual skills, which in turn will ensure their competitiveness in the labor market and to raise the prestige of polylingual education.

The main task of the modern higher school is to train a specialist capable of interlanguage professional dialogue and active cooperation with polylingual world. Given the fact that universities build the way academic and professional mobility of future specialists, their introduction to the polylingual educational environment is especially important and becomes urgent the question of readiness of future teachers to professional activity in such an environment. There is need to implement new methodological approach and to identify effective modalities for the training of students in polylingual educational environment.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of this article is to consider the task and justification of the theoretical foundations of polylingual educational environment in higher school as a condition of professional training of future

bilingual teachers of, able to teach their subjects in two languages. Objectives of the study are to:

- 1) consider the global and Russian experience of development of the theoretical foundations of multilingual education;
- 2) suggest the author's definition of “polylingual educational environment” and “teacher-bilingua”;
- 3) analyze the possibility of creating a polylingual educational environment in the Republic of Tatarstan.

Literature review

At present holistic views and approaches to the creation of polylingual educational environment are gaining increasing popularity, however, their implementation in Russia is still not widespread.

The development of the theoretical foundations of multilingualism and multilingual education belongs to European scientists. The issues related to multilingual education in Europe was widely discussed and became relevant in the second half of the 20th century, which resulted in the intensification of research in many branches of knowledge. Up to a certain time, some researchers have expressed the negative attitude to multilingual learning and use in training and everyday life of children more than one language considered it harmful.

Thanks to the scientific work of Canadian, scientists Perl and Lambert (1962) attitudes to multilingualism have changed. In 1962, based on experimental data, scientists have demonstrated cognitive and socio-cultural benefits of learning more than one language.

A significant contribution to the development of the theory of multicultural education has made Vivian (1995). The scientist suggested that a holistic approach to the study of aspects of multilingualism. He considered the concept of multicompetence as a unique form of language competence of the individual that speaks two languages.

The trend of increasing importance of major conceptual ideas of multilingualism and multicompetence noted Australian scientist Jessner (2008). The main provisions of this trend have performed a complete lifting of the ban use at lessons of the native language.

American expert in the field of linguistics Krashen (2009) in her research paper writes that at the beginning of the new century, foreign scientists increasing interest in the study of the question of the use in learning a third language, a characteristic feature of performing comparative-contrastive study of several languages, drawing on the knowledge gained in their native language. This feature provided the ability to transfer knowledge and skills from one language to another.

Now multilingual education in Europe presents a rapidly growing industry with multiple numbers of varieties. It is based on the idea that multilingualism identity arises in the process of extending language experience. People can use the knowledge of several languages for the understanding of spoken or written text him earlier on the implicit language through oral or written text in an unknown language to him earlier due to the learning of words that have a similar sound or spelling in several languages in the “new form” (Council of Europe, 2006).

Lately multilingual education in Russia has become the object of attention. Interest in the creation of polylingual educational environment increased after bilingual education was actively used in educational practice.

As believed by Bahtikireeva and Tashenov (2004), in spite of all the positive aspects of multilingual education, it requires the implementation of appropriate programs and appeal to the ethno-cultural component, which involves an idea of the richness of the national culture, spiritual values of the people, its history and language. In conditions of polylingual educational environment in the higher school there is a need to provide teachers appropriate bilingual environment and in professional activities – school environment.

Modern trends of training specialists for work in a multilingual space considered in the scientific work of Khazhgalieva (2018), where the author proves that this space possesses a pragmatic potential for the development of the individual student, as well as training of future specialist to function in an information society.

The article Dzaparova (2016) presented the main directions of development of the polylingual model of polycultural education in the conditions of preservation of national minority languages. The high results that can be achieved with the implementation of this multilingual model are demonstrated by the example of one of the constituent entities of the Russian Federation - the Republic of North Ossetia-Alania.

The problems of multilingual education in the Republic of Dagestan are highlighted in the work of Magomedov (2019). According to the author, one of the urgent tasks of today in the Republic of Dagestan is to organize successful integration into the global educational space and provide students with access to relevant information in any of three languages: Dagestan, Russian and English.

In the educational practice of the Russian Federation, there are two main learning models that are aimed at the formation and development of competencies in the context of natural bilingualism:

- 1) full immersion, i.e. transition to training in full in Russian;

2) a transitional model, when two languages are used at the initial stage of training (national and Russian), and gradually going the transition to training in Russian is on (Danilov, 2019).

There are various scientific studies on the development of transitional models of bilingual education in the Republic of Tatarstan. For example, Miftahova (2013) proposes to apply the system of adaptive teaching students in a bilingual (Russian-Tatar) basis, which is aimed at successful adaptation (to achieve a high level of adaptivity) bilingual students to the educational activities at the University. The main difficulty in the period of adaptation training, according to the author, is to overcome the language barrier during the development of the conceptual and terminological apparatus of the discipline in a second language. The author proposes a solution to the problem, resorting to adaptive strategies of adaptation, i.e. adaptation to the specific conditions in which the educational process.

In the work of Tuktamyshov (2000) studied and revealed the socio-economic bases of transition to bilingual (Tatar-Russian) education in high schools. According to the author, the transition to bilingual education in the higher school it is necessary to consider two conditions:

- 1) At a higher education institution should be created conditions for education in native language;
- 2) Persons who are studying in their native language, should be proficient in the Russian language.

The author identifies two main problems associated with the transition to bilingual education in high school:

- 1) Shortage of national teaching staff, who know the Tatar language at the level allowing for teaching it;
- 2) The lack of original training and methodological support in the Tatar language.

The solution to the second problem can be achieved through the creation of educational materials, textbooks and educational-methodical complexes on disciplines of the Tatar language, tailored to local circumstances.

The definition of theoretical prerequisites, stages and directions of formation of the national bilingual education by means of native and foreign languages enables us to develop and confirm a holistic concept of bilingual education at the higher pedagogical school.

Methodology

In the framework of the research, we used theoretical methods, among which there are analysis of the issue of creating a polylingual educational environment in the process of preparation of the teacher-bilingual based on the study of educational-methodical and scientific-pedagogical literature.

A leading approach to the study of problems of formation of the polylingual personality is based on the system analysis of specific features of training of future teacher-bilingual in conditions of polylingual educational environment.

Results s

The relevance of multilingual education for Tatarstan leaves a problematic issue associated with the organization of polylingual educational environment. In order to substantiate the theoretical basis of polylingual educational environment in higher school as a condition of professional training of future teachers of bilingual, able to teach their subjects in two languages, it is necessary to disclose the essence of the concept «polylingual educational environment» and find out who the bilingual teacher is. In addition, the study should identify the specific features of the polylingual educational environment in higher education, describe the existing experience and propose specific methods to work in this environment.

In the phrase “polylingual educational environment” are concepts such as environment, educational environment and polylinguality. Environment, speaking on the subject of study of sociology, philosophy, psychology and, of course, pedagogy is defined as an environment and set of conditions where the activity of man in society. In the modern education environment acts as:

- 1) The conditions in which man exists and lives around him, bringing people who are connected with the community of nature and livelihoods.
- 2) A social space, an area of free activity of the individual, where it is the development and implementation of action.

Explanatory dictionary of Russian of Ozhegov (2015) gives the following definition of environment: «the Surrounding social conditions, the environment, and also a collection of people bound by generality of these conditions». In a foreign language, the environment is considered to be one of the most frequently used words and is interpreted as the environment, the situation, the external environment in a certain space (New Webster's Dictionary and Thesaurus of the English Language, 2003; Longman Dictionary of English Language and Culture, 2005).

Jasvin (2001) considers the educational environment as a special organized process of purposeful formation of the personality in a socially determined pattern.

Polylinguality as the trend of the 21st century is primarily the prestige of the language. In our study polylingual educational environment we consider as a system specially created conditions for the

implementation of the learning process in several languages surrounding the subjects of the educational process, as well as the combination of these elements associated with the commonality of these terms.

To identify the specific characteristics of polylingual educational environment, assume likely end results training teachers for bilingual under such conditions that clearly differ from the results of training of future specialists in the regular education environment.

In conditions of polylingual educational environment is formed by a number of abilities of individuals: a high level of linguistic and cultural knowledge, fluency in several languages and apply them in various situations, including a professional. In this regard, it is logical to assume that teacher-bilingual is a teacher, equally fluent in several languages and is able to apply their skills within the educational process (in teaching subject matter, communication with students, etc.).

The need and specifics of preparation of future teachers for bilingual in conditions of polylingual educational environment may be determined by the following factors:

- 1) The social order, involving the implementation of a system of multilingual education, for example, in countries and territories with multi-ethnic population;
- 2) Academic mobility of students, defining ways of integrating students into the world educational environment;
- 3) The use of teachers communication technology as a universal tool;
- 4) By adjusting the content of higher education, taking into account the necessity of familiarizing future specialists with the knowledge of other cultures.

Summarizing the analyzed situation, we will describe polylingual educational environment as a set of four vector fields:

The substantive focus determines the saturation of the educational process of linguistic and cultural knowledge of how to maintain the interest in national culture, and the optimal orientation in another.

Activity and event focus provides the content of educational process, a variety of events that help to involve students in cultural heritage and develop positive attitude to linguistic and cultural diversity. A value-oriented orientation introduces students to national values: the language, history and culture of their people, as well as personality-oriented values: to ideal, self-development, multicultural and multilingual personality.

The communicative and normative orientation involves the reorientation of the goals of education, which are based on respect for the traditions and languages of different peoples and the diversity of cultures, taking into account the principle of multilingualism to form a holistic picture of the world.

Recently in the Republic of Tatarstan, the issues of learning on the basis of polylingual paid attention. Today, much has been done for the formation of normative – legal base of modern polylingual educational environment. However, can we talk about the strength of the paved path?

In many dictionaries, the polylinguism translates as multilingualism, which is a means of expression and understanding of reality and a way of communication in a circle of multilinguals. It should be noted that personality is primarily realized through language. And when it comes to multilingual education, quality study and using of native language in learning subject should be given utmost importance.

Currently, in many regions of Russia, including the Republic of Tatarstan is the development trend of the national-Russian bilingualism, and not multilingualism. However, the level of bilingualism in the educational system does not always meet modern requirements. This is largely determined by the use of mixed bilingualism, which is manifested in the process of communication and learning discipline in their native language, using sentences, half of which consists of Russian.

The problem of formation and development of multilingualism is always addressed in studies of scientists of different nations. Noting the importance of knowledge of foreign languages, wherein scientists emphasized the need for introducing students primarily for the native language. About this in his writings repeatedly testify and the founder of scientific pedagogy in Russia Ushinsky (1974).

By lingua-didactic concept of the founder of pedagogical science Comenius (1987), literate person should know a few languages: native language – ‘for private life’, the languages of neighboring peoples to ‘chat’ with them, Latin ‘to read scientific literature’ and additionally: ‘for the philosophers and physicians the Greek and Arabic languages, for Theologians – Greek and Hebrew’. In this approach, special preference was given to native and Latin languages, which need to study at the same level. This interpretation of Jan Amos Comenius once again emphasizes the necessity of knowing the native language.

The Republic of Tatarstan is considered a Russian region with natural polylingual environment and stable inter-ethnic relations. In the monograph under the editorship of Yarmakeev (2015) noted that polylingual education aimed at eliminating the linguistic barrier, discouraging to effective export and import innovative cultural and educational products and technologies. Noticed linguistic barrier hinders

not only the development of a strategy for harmonization of intercultural and linguistic issues in RT, but also prevents the full integration of the education system of the Republic in the all-Russian and international cultural and educational space.

Until a certain time a particular interest of educational institutions of Tatarstan aroused the bilingual education. Due to the development on the world stage polylingual education of the Tatarstan educational institutions at various levels began to learn from the experience and take the first steps in the creation of polylingual educational institutions.

The initiator of creation in Tatarstan, not just schools, but whole complexes of polylingual was made by Tatarstan state Counsellor Mintimer Shaimiev. The concept of polylingual complex has been discussed quite thoroughly and continues to be considered at the meetings with representatives of the Ministry of education and science of RT. So, during one of such meetings it was announced that by 2022, the Republic will be six of polylingual schools, in which students will, in addition to Russian, to learn the Tatar and English languages.

It should be noted that in Kazan there are already prelingually school. A vivid example can be «Multidisciplinary polylingual gymnasium No. 180», which has all the conditions for social, intellectual and personal development of individuality of the speaker and prepares functionally competent polylingual and polycultural personality. The strategic goal of the school is the formation of polycultural educational space, which corresponds to the current state and prospects of development of the multiethnic, multilingual, multiconfessional Russian society and the state. In their teaching activities polylingual representatives of the school implement the idea of the dialogue approach and the concept of «dialogue of cultures» that get involved to different cultures, the formation of planetary consciousness, allowing you to work closely with representatives of various countries and peoples, and to integrate into the global and pan-European cultural and educational space.

Each of created in the Republic of polylingual schools will have their own specifics related to the targets, profile the characteristics of individual students, and, most importantly, personnel potential. Today there is a question about creating training programs and teacher training for polylingual schools.

The republic already has experience in training bilingual teachers. Since 2018, at the initiative of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Tatarstan, on the basis of the Kazan Federal University (KFU), training is being provided for future teachers who are able to teach their subject in Tatar and Russian.

The greatest interest in creating a multilingual educational environment is the experience of other countries. So, in Kazakhstan, the system of multilingual education is being introduced both into the system of general and higher education. On the need for development at least three languages in their country were spoken by Nursultan Nazarbayev, the ex-president of Kazakhstan. Three languages mean the Kazakh language (as the state language), Russian (as the language of interethnic communication) and English (as the language of successful entry into the global economy).

In Kazakhstani schools, trilingual education is introduced in stages, and this is characteristic of physico - mathematical and natural sciences. In some universities of this country, for example, North Kazakhstan State University, multilingual education is conducted in the same areas of training. In this regard, educational institutions adhere to a certain ratio, indicated in the curriculum in Kazakhstan - 50/30/20. In other words, 50% of courses are taught in the language of instruction – Kazakh, 30% of disciplines - in English and 20% using the second language of instruction, that is, the Russian.

The study revealed that the universities of Kazakhstan faced with the same problems that arise when developing methods of polylingual education in the Republic of Tatarstan. Scientists around the world working to solve these problems, interested in another important question: how to prepare specialists, who will professionally own mother tongue and two foreign languages, able to simultaneously resort to them in the framework of the educational process. Kazakhstan teachers are out of the existing situation, developing and subsequent publishing dictionaries with translations of the national words in Russian and English. In the creation of such dictionaries there have been involved as teachers of the subject, and experts who are fluent in Kazakh, English and Russian languages.

For successful work in polylingual educational environment of the University it is necessary to resort to diverse methods, which will provide self-development and the formation of polylingual personality of a future specialist. One of the most common pedagogical techniques, aimed at the study of the subject with the use of a foreign language and learning a foreign language through the subject technology is a CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning). The technology described by David Marsh, a researcher from Finland, working in the field of multilingualism and bilingualism, and soon it was translated into Russian language called «subject -language integrated learning». The implementation of the CLIL methodology involves the formation of polylingual groups, the choice of an appropriate language-learning audience and following components of the methodology (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Designer technology CLIL

Applying the technology of CLIL in the educational process, you should consider a few rules: choose a theme according to the interest of the students, to select lexical material in accordance with the level of proficiency in the language group, select appropriate grammatical structures, necessarily use text and make bright graphic organizer. Given that a graphic organizer is a tool of written communication, which promotes the representation of knowledge and competence, the last rule acts as a good means of activation of cognitive activity of students. Besides, didactic basics of graphic organizer perform illustrative, communicative and cognitive functions. In the educational process different forms of graphic organizers that can be divided into sequential (scaling), hierarchical (pyramid), a graphical comparison (chart), or conceptual (concept – maps) organizers.

Fragments of CLIL methodic can be used on any object with the use of sets of techniques. One of such techniques – ‘True-False Dictation’ or ‘True or false’. The teacher sets several sentences on a certain topic. If the sentence is true, students write a sentence in their native language. If the sentence is false, students must convert it to true and write down already in a foreign language.

CLIL technology is actively used and employees at KFU. The Department of bilingual and digital education operates a training and research laboratory of CLIL. Teachers of the Department with great interest, studying the experience of technology use CLIL in foreign educational practice, to develop lectures, seminars, educational materials, technology-based CLIL, organize workshops and conduct courses on the use of CLIL technology in the domestic educational institutions, as well as doing research and actively participate in scientific conferences in the field of polylingual education.

Another technique is to work in polylingual educational environment can be a technology LLGC, which promotes the study of speech culture and traditions of other nationalities. The technique is hidden in its abbreviation: I – language, L – logic, G – game, C – culture. LLGC» technology is aimed by means of language on the development of personality. The implementation of this technology involves three phases: diagnostic (testing of the initial educational level of students in polylingual educational environment), project (the application of game techniques with appeal to culturological and multilingual component), organizational - creative (interaction in polylingual educational environment with using the concepts ‘want’, ‘know’, ‘do’, ‘evaluate’, ‘create’).

Pedagogical tools for the teacher today are quite diverse. Formed and a wide range of techniques for optimum performance in polylingual educational environment.

Polylingual educational environment today is an important component of modern education and contributes to the education of students in the spirit of respect for native language, national culture and language acquisition and traditions of other peoples. Globalization processes in higher education, current trends suggest the creation of polylingual educational environment at the University. The study of several languages in the process of professional preparation of future teachers for bilingual helps to involve students in world culture and allows you to think about the creation of polylingual educational environment.

Discussions

The multilingual educational environment today is the most important component of modern education and helps to educate students in the spirit of respect for their native language, national culture, as well as the assimilation of languages and traditions of other nations.

In our understanding, the organization of the educational process in a multilingual educational environment is accompanied not only by the study of languages, dialogue of cultures and mutual enrichment of national values, but also by the creation of conditions for self-development and self-realization in the modern multilingual world. The basic idea in the framework of creating a multilingual educational environment and building the path to multilingualism is to stimulate the use of primarily the native language.

A multilingual educational environment, acting as one of the requirements for modern education, needs a specific approach. Despite all the positive aspects of the multilingual environment, it requires the implementation of appropriate programs and appeal to the ethnocultural component. Future specialists face

the most important task of creating the ability to build communication and carry out professional activities in their native and foreign languages, respect the traditions and language of their people, and honor the values of other cultures.

Conclusion

The globalization processes that occur in the field of higher education presuppose modern trends in creating a multilingual educational environment in higher education – a system of specially created conditions for the implementation of the learning process in several languages, surrounding the subjects of the educational process, also the totality of these subjects, related to the commonality of these conditions. The creation of a multilingual educational environment in the process of training helps students become familiar with world culture, forms the multilingual personality of the future bilingual teacher – equally speaking in several languages and able to apply his skills in the educational process (when educating the subject, communicating with students, etc.).

The study allows us to conclude that it is possible to create a multilingual educational environment in the process of training bilingual teachers for the Republic of Tatarstan. A significant argument in favor of creating a university multilingual educational environment can be the development of the concept of multilingual schools in the Republic of Tatarstan, for which bilingual teachers are training.

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